

Growing entropy as an alternative to dark energy

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Abstract

To avoid the dark energy hypothesis, we look at a frame of reference that is at rest relative to the dipole-corrected cosmic microwave background radiation, and in it a metric in which each observer assigns a time dilatation to all other bodies depending on their distance. Based on our metric we establish the Einstein field equations for weak fields. The radial equation can be interpreted as Fokker-Planck equation of entropy; thereby, we link entropy to the length of the time interval available for a transmitted unit of information. The growth of entropy leads to a dissipating force related to the change in Helmholtz free energy, which drives the accelerated expansion of the universe. In our approach, the light of recently observed massive galaxies with $7,4 < z < 9,1$ is emitted not 500 – 700 Myr after the big bang, but later than half the age of the universe.

1. Introduction

The currently preferred cosmological models are based on the RW-metric, which leads to the Friedmann field equations. The prevalent model in cosmology, the Λ CDM model, is based on these equations. Nevertheless, it runs into severe difficulties: Taking into account the accelerated expansion of the universe, one has to introduce a repulsive component, called dark energy, whose physical nature is enigmatic.

A number of ideas have been proposed to avoid the dark energy hypothesis. As in our approach, Easson et al. [1] proposed entropy accelerating the universe; but there, underlying the RW-metric, entropy is associated with the holographic information storage on the surface screen placed at the horizon of the universe. Here, we work without this concept. Farnes [2] proposed a modified Λ CDM model, where continuously created negative masses can explain both, dark energy as well as dark matter phenomena. Intensive work over 12 years, based on the RW-metric, has been done in the TRR 33 collaboration [3] without a conclusive breakthrough. Hauret and Magain [4] proposed a modification of the RW-metric by introducing a cosmological time τ in order not to have to rely on the hypothesis of dark energy. We feel that their idea is pioneering. However, the cosmological time τ itself is linked to the curvature of spacetime thus exceeding the scope of the underlying RW-metric.

Using the RW-metric, the redshift of the radiation emitted from distant sources correlates with the growth of the cosmic scale factor $R(t)$, while the time t measured in an locally inertial moving reference frame flows uniformly in the universe. In our approach however, we are dropping the hypothesis of a uniform time flow thereby leaving the framework of comoving coordinate systems. We assume, that any observer in space possesses only its own, local time scale. Due to the principle of cosmology, the time scales of

observers should equal each others. Isotropy of space demands that the time flow does not depend on the direction in space; so, the redshift of the radiation which is emitted by distant sources and absorbed at the position of an observer has to be isotrop. This isotropy is guaranteed if we choose a frame of reference which is at rest relative to the dipole corrected cosmic microwave background (cmb) radiation; the origin as position of the observer is freely selectable. Independent of cosmological models, the baryonic acoustic oscillations of the cmb show that the spatial curvature of space-time is indistinguishable from zero; we take this into account by putting the radial scale factor of our metric to be one.

Whereas usually, 'mass grips spacetime, telling it how to curve' [5], here, we will not start with a given stress-energy tensor, but propose our metric in sec. 2 and examine the properties of the corresponding stress-energy tensor in sec. 7. Underlying our metric, we establish the Einstein field equations for slowly varying variables as expected for the present and future universe in sec. 3. In sec. 4, we propose a solution of the field equations, which includes a distance-dependent time dilatation which is ascribed to an object at the distance r by an observer at his position $r_0 = 0$. We may consider this solution as an extension of the well known effect in special relativity, that any observer in his local inertial frame of reference ascribes a time dilatation to all other driveless moving objects, even reciprocally. The equations of the geodesic lines are evaluated in sec. 5 and illustrated in sec. 6, showing, that any observer notices a escape drift of all bodies away from his own position and a temporal growing redshift of the cmb. At greater distances, the timescale depends weaker on the distance than in the immediate vicinity of the observer; so, one does not expect the redshift to follow Hubble's law.

In sec. 8, we notice, that the radial equation has the shape of the flux equation of entropy s , the Fokker-Planck equation, if

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s is interpreted as the period of time which is disposable for one unit of information to be transmitted. In sec. 9, we discuss free Helmholtz entropy determining the expansion rate of the universe.

The empirical redshift-distance law of the SNIa radiation [9] is qualitatively interpreted in sec. 10. In our approach, the light of recently observed massive galaxies with $7,4 < z < 9,1$ is emitted not only 500 – 700 Myr after the big bang, but later than half of the age of the universe.

2. The metric

In order to motivate our metric, we start with a gaussian geodesic metric [6] with line element

$$ds^2 = du^2 - G \cdot dv^2,$$

thus omitting angular coordinates. In the case of the spatially flat RW-metric, we can identify G with the cosmic radial scale factor $R(t)$, u with the time coordinate $u = c \cdot t$ and v with the distance r . In our metric however, we swap the roles of u and v ; we are entitled to do so because an extension of the wavelength of an observed radiation cannot be distinguished from a reduction in frequency. We use the line element

$$ds^2 = C(r, t)c^2 dt^2 - dr^2 - r^2 d\vartheta^2 - r^2 d\varphi^2 \sin\theta. \quad (1)$$

Here, $\sqrt{C(r, t)}$ is the number of time units passing in the distance r from an observer at $r_0 = 0$, if he measures one time unit for himself. In his present at time t_0 , he may set $\sqrt{C(0, t_0)} = 1$. As shown in sec. 5, t_0 can be selected freely in our approach. Whereas, due to the principle of cosmology, $R(t)$ depends only on time t , $C(r, t)$ may vary with time t and distance r .

Before the detection of the cosmic microwave background (cmb) radiation, the RW-metric was the only conceivable frame of reference. In our approach, the frame of reference has to be at rest relative to the dipole corrected cmb; thus, the isotropy of space is guaranteed.

Our metric has to describe two opposite evolutionary tendencies of the universe: the contraction due to the gravitation and the accelerated expansion which we will ascribe to growing entropy in sec. 8. So,

$$\sqrt{C} = \sqrt{A \cdot B} \quad (2)$$

is factorised in two parts. Regarding the future of the universe, where gravitation is expected to loose importance, we assume, that the first factor $\sqrt{A} \approx 1 + \frac{\Phi}{c^2}$, with attracting gravitational potential Φ hardly deviates from one. Until section 9, we will consider only the second part, \sqrt{B} .

3. The Einstein field equations

The metric (1) determines the formulas for the Einstein field equations. Here, we consider only terms varying weakly with t and r , as expected in the future universe; so, the early universe is not considered. Thus, we start with the Ricci-tensor in linear approximation

$$R_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\rho}^{\rho}}{\partial x^{\nu}} - \frac{\partial \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\rho}}{\partial x^{\rho}}. \quad (3)$$

The tensor elements in the field equations are given in Tab. 1. While $B(r, t)$ can be time-dependent, the tensor elements contain only derivatives with respect to the distance r ; we mark them with dashes.

The spherical stress-energy tensor with energy density ρ and pressure p using metric (1) is

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \text{diag}(\rho \cdot B, p, p \cdot r^2, p \cdot r^2). \quad (4)$$

It will be considered in sec. 7.

Ricci tensorelement R_{00}	$-\frac{1}{2}B''$
Ricci tensorelement R_{11}	$\left(\frac{B'}{2B}\right)' - \frac{2}{r^2}$
Ricci tensorelement R_{22}	0
Riemannscalar $-\frac{Ri}{2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{B}''}{\sqrt{B}} - \frac{1}{r^2}$
Einstein tensorelement G_{00}	$B \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{4}\left(\frac{B'}{B}\right)^2 - \frac{1}{r^2}\right)$
Einstein tensorelement G_{11}	$-\frac{1}{4} \cdot \left(\frac{B'}{B}\right)^2 - \frac{1}{r^2}$
Einstein tensorelement G_{22}	$-r^2 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{B}''}{\sqrt{B}} + 1$

Tab. 1: Tensor elements of the Einstein field equations for weak fields, based on the metric eq. (1) with $A(r, t) \approx 1$.

Herewith, the field equations are calculated: ($G_{22} = G_{33}$, $\kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}$, $G = \text{constant of gravitation}$)

$$R_{00} - B \cdot \frac{Ri}{2} = G_{00} = -\kappa \cdot T_{00} \text{ or} \\ -\left(\frac{\sqrt{B}'}{\sqrt{B}}\right)^2 - \frac{1}{r^2} = -\kappa \cdot \rho \quad (5)$$

$$R_{11} + \frac{Ri}{2} = G_{11} = -\kappa \cdot T_{11} \text{ or} \\ -\left(\frac{\sqrt{B}'}{\sqrt{B}}\right)^2 - \frac{1}{r^2} = -\kappa \cdot p \quad (6)$$

$$R_{22} + \frac{r^2}{2} \cdot Ri = G_{22} = -\kappa \cdot T_{22} \text{ or} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{B}''}{\sqrt{B}} + \frac{1}{r^2} = -\kappa \cdot p \quad (7)$$

4. Solutions of the field equations

Assuming that the universe is homogenous, we seek solutions with spatially constant p and ρ for very large distances r ($\frac{1}{r^2} \approx 0$). In this limit, $\left(\frac{\sqrt{B}'}{\sqrt{B}}\right)^2$ in eqs. (5) and (6) should not depend on r . The metric with scale factor $\sqrt{B(r, t)}$ must be time-dependent; so, the solution of the eqs. (5), (6), (7) is

$$\sqrt{B(r, t)} = \exp(-a \cdot \frac{r-r_0}{c(t-t_0)}) \quad (8)$$

with constant $a > 0$. So, at all fixed locations $r - r_0 > 0$, the unit of time increases and thus the frequency of radiation emitting sources decreases with growing distance r . At the position of an observer at $r = r_0$, $\sqrt{B(0,t)} = 1$, independent of the time t .

With $V(r) = \frac{r-r_0}{a}$, we can write eq. (8) in the diffusion form

$$\sqrt{B(r,t)} = \exp\left(-\frac{(r-r_0)^2}{V(r) \cdot c(t-t_0)}\right).$$

The Riemannscalar $Ri = -\frac{2 \cdot a^2}{c^2(t-t_0)^2}$ is independent of the freely selectable position of an observer at r_0 ; thus, the principle of cosmology is fulfilled. In the following, we choose $r_0 = 0$.

In the exponential function eq. (8), we choose the negative sign. We justify this considering Minkowski spacetime as a limit of curved spacetime for weak fields: there, any observer in his local inertial system ascribes a time dilatation with $\sqrt{B} < 1$ to any other moved inertial system, even reciprocally. This also applies to differences of velocities, i.e. to driveless motions in gravitational fields. Geodesic lines in spacetime glide over in Minkowskian worldlines without rupture of the local metric. Due to the negative sign, for $t > t_0$, we represent an expanding universe with density $\rho(t)$ and pressure $p(t)$ in eqs. (5) and (6) diminishing with time t according to $\rho = p \sim \left(\frac{a}{c(t-t_0)}\right)^2$.

5. The equations of motion

We note the equations of geodesic lines with Christoffel symbols $\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\lambda$ ($\lambda = 0, \dots, 3$):

$$\frac{d^2 x^\lambda}{ds^2} = -\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\lambda \frac{dx^\mu}{ds} \frac{dx^\nu}{ds}. \quad (9)$$

Here, we look for the equations of a body moving in radial direction ($\lambda = 0,1$) in our time-varying gravitational field:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{c \cdot d^2 t}{ds^2} &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial u} \log(B) \cdot \frac{c \cdot dt}{ds} \cdot \frac{dr}{ds} - \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \log(B) \cdot \left(\frac{c \cdot dt}{ds}\right)^2 \\ \frac{d^2 r}{ds^2} &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{dB}{dr} \cdot \left(\frac{c \cdot dt}{ds}\right)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

We integrate the first eq. (10) ($\lambda = 0$); with an appropriate constant of integration, we get

$$\frac{c \cdot dt}{ds} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{B}}. \quad (11)$$

So, we interpret s/c as the proper time τ of the moving body, $ds = d\tau = \sqrt{B} \cdot c \cdot dt$.

The two differential equations eq. (10) can be solved iteratively to calculate velocities and positions of a body moving along a geodesic line. By this way, the geodesics have been drawn in Fig. 1. There, the curvature of the surface is held constant. Herewith, the Fig. 2 shows the distance traveled by a receding body as it is measured in the local coordinates of the pseudosphere. The body starts at $r_0 = 0$ at the time $\tau_0 = 0$ with starting velocity $v_0 = 0$. The plot coincides in good approximation with the straight dashed line which corresponds to a uniform motion of the body.

6. Illustration of the escape motion of bodies

In Fig. 1, we present the radial dependence of $\sqrt{B(r)}$ based on the metric eq. (8) as a snapshot for constant time t . Different to the usual presentation, the time axis is directed to the right side and the distance r upwards on the curved surface – the pseudosphere – according to the presentation in graphical timetables. The position of an observer is below at $r_0 = 0$. With increasing r , the growing time intervals in the grid correspond to a growing time dilatation, $\sqrt{B(r)} < 1$, as seen from the position $r_0 = 0$. The three curves drawn in Fig. 1 are geodesics starting at the time $t - t_0 = 0$ with different velocities v_0 , the lower geodesic with $v_0 = 0$; during their run, the grid is fixed. Due to the locally dependent time dilatation $\sqrt{B(r)}$ an observer at an arbitrary position $r_0 = 0$ will observe a radially symmetric escape movement of all other bodies, even mutually. Seen from outside the curved coordinate grid, this motion appears accelerated in the direction of increasing distance r .

Fig. 1: Gaussian geodesic grid of the the surface with a constant negative Riemann scalar (pseudosphere). In the physical context of the RW-metric, the vertical geodesic lines are the time axes when positions are fixed and the orthogonal horizontal lines describe the possible positions of bodies at fixed times. Thus, an exponentially expanding universe is illustrated by a radius $R(t)$ of the pseudosphere growing exponentially with time. However, in our context, the vertical geodesics show the radial distances r of bodies to an observer below at position $r_0 = 0$, the horizontal curved lines represent time axes at the various positions r . Three geodesics all starting at the position $r_0 = 0$ with different initial velocities v_0 are calculated iteratively and drawn in the pseudosphere. Due to the time dilatation growing exponentially with distance r , geodesic lines all exhibit an escape drift away from the position at $r_0 = 0$. The lowest starts with $v_0 = 0$. Based on the local coordinates of the pseudosphere, observers move uniformly along their geodesic lines. On the other hand, their motion appears to be accelerated, if considered from outside the surface.

Fig. 2. Distance r traveled by a body; it is calculated iteratively using eq. (10) based on the local coordinates of the pseudosphere. The body starts at $r_0 = 0$ at the time $\tau_0 = \frac{s}{c} = 0$ with starting velocity $v_0 = 0$. The units of the distance r and the velocity v in Fig. 2 are not fitted to experimental data but calculated in order to display the essential features.

7. Interpretation of the stress-energy tensor

Whereas usually, energy density ρ and pressure p are given and the metric is derived, here, we have proposed the metric in sec. 2; what can we say about the appropriate stress-energy tensor? Since $G_{00} = G_{11}$ (see eqs. (5), (6)), it follows that $p = \rho$. To interpret this result, we consider a thin spherical mass bubble with radius r : Inside the bubble, the gravitational field energy is vanishing, outside, it is negative. If we enlarge the bubble by dr without changing the mass volume and mass energy of the bubble itself, the field outside of $r + dr$ does not change; this is shown, similar to the derivation of the Birkhoff theorem, by writing down the Ricci tensor element $R_{01} = 0$ for an isotrope, time dependent radially symmetric metric [6]. By increasing the energy density within the spherical mass shell with thickness dr from negative values to zero, the increase of the gravitational energy of the system, $\rho \cdot dV$, is completely provided by the pressure work $p \cdot dV$.

Using eqs. (10), (11) for the acceleration g , we get

$$\frac{d^2r}{ds^2} = g(s) = -\frac{\sqrt{B}}{B} \quad (12)$$

Here, g is related to the proper time $\tau = \frac{s}{c}$.

Due to eq. (12), the field equation eq. (5) can be expressed as

$$G_{00} = \kappa \cdot \frac{c^4}{8\pi G} \cdot \frac{1}{c^4} \cdot \left(\frac{d^2r}{ds^2}\right)^2 = \kappa \cdot \frac{1}{8\pi G} \cdot g^2. \quad (13)$$

Thus, T_{00} coincides with the classical formula for the energy density of a gravitational field, $\rho = -\frac{1}{8\pi G} \cdot g^2$, with the local proper time $\tau = ds/c$ underlying the acceleration g in the distance r from an observer. Whereas in classical theory, the reference distance r , where $\sqrt{B(r)} = 1$ lies in infinity, here, it is localized at the position of any observer; thus, the sign is reversed.

In General Relativity, severe problems arise when gravitational field energy has to be incorporated in the Einstein field equations: there, the energy-stress tensor determinates the curvature of spacetime, but in turn, curvature of spacetime is connected with energy and mass. For the case of weak fields, post-Newtonian approximations [8] are frequently used in which the non-linear, quadratic terms in the Einstein tensor on the left side of the field equations are assumed to be part of the stress-energy tensor on the right side of the field equations. Here, the Einstein tensor elements G_{00} and G_{11} which we calculate based on the metric eq. (8) consist exclusively of such terms; this is expected, since in eq. (8), we have not considered the gravitational part \sqrt{A} of the metric in eq. (2).

8. Information theoretical analysis of eq. (5)

Electromagnetic waves transport information; here, we consider the connection between transported information and time dilatation \sqrt{B} by means of an thought experiment using toy units: a wave, which is emitted with frequency $f_A = 1$ Hz at a distant position A is detected at position B with frequency $f_B = 0,5$ Hz. An observer at A may assume that the wave transports an information of 2 bit per s (e.g. in two halfwaves); then, B will receive in his second only 1 bit. On the other hand, the information of 1 bit disposes over a time intervall of 0,5 s at position A, but of 1 s in the time scale of position B. This growth of temporally freedom corresponds to the growth of the available volume e.g. in a diffusion process with growing entropy. Since \sqrt{B} is doubled when going from A to B, we may connect the content σ of information (entropy) per second with time dilatation \sqrt{B} by

$$\sigma = \log(\sqrt{B}). \quad (14)$$

If for example we have $\sqrt{B} > 1$, the time scale is shortened and $\sigma > 1$ bit.

We define $j := -\frac{d\sigma}{dr}$ as the flux density of entropy.

Now, we wish to investigate the connection between the entropy eq. (14) and the radial field equation eq. (6). To do so, we first consider a general smooth function $f(r, t)$ which obeys the Fokker-Planck equation with vanishing drift coefficient [7]:

$$\dot{f}(r, t) = V(r) \cdot f''(r, t). \quad (15)$$

Here, the dot means the partial derivate with respect to the time t and the dashes the derivatives with respect to the distance r . If V is constant, eq. (15) reduces to the diffusion equation. Eq. (15) can be transformed into a flux equation of entropy s : Dividing by f , we get

$$\frac{\dot{f}}{f} = V \cdot \frac{f''}{f} = V \cdot \left(\left(\frac{f'}{f}\right)' + \left(\frac{f'}{f}\right)^2 \right) \quad \text{or}$$

$$\log \dot{f} = V \cdot \left((\log f)'' + ((\log f)')^2 \right).$$

With $s_{FP} = \log(f)$ eq. (15) can be written as

$$\dot{s}_{FP} = V \cdot (s_{FP}'' + (s_{FP}')^2) = V \cdot (-j_{FP}' + j_{FP}^2). \quad (16)$$

Here, $s_{FP}'' = -j_{FP}'$ describes the change of the flux of entropy and j_{FP}^2 is the source term of entropy.

We compare eq. (6) with eq. (16): for large r , the radial field equation (6) can be interpreted as constituent of the Fokker-Planck equation

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\sigma} &= V \cdot (\log(\sqrt{B})'' + (\log\sqrt{B})'^2) \\ &= V \cdot (-j' + j^2),\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

where $j = -\sigma' = -\log(\sqrt{B})'$ is the flux density of information. The source term of entropy, j^2 , is represented by the tensor element $G_{00} = G_{11}$ and the flow change j' is given by the Ricci Tensorelement R_{11} . The temporal evolution of entropy

$$\dot{\sigma} = -V \cdot \frac{Ri}{2} > 0 \quad (18)$$

is proportional to the Rieman scalar Ri ; it is positive definite, as required by the principle of entropy.

In our approach, the acceleration of the escape drift of the universe,

$$\frac{g}{c^2} = j = -\sigma' = -\log(\sqrt{B})' \quad (19)$$

is opposite to the attraction produced by distant gravitating masses, described by the factor $\sqrt{A} \approx 1 + \frac{\Phi}{c^2}$; it is connected to the flux j of entropy σ .

9. Thermodynamical aspects

We now incorporate attracting gravitation in our model and compare it with a simple thermodynamical description. Due to eq. (2), the gravitation is described by a timescale $\sqrt{A(r)} > 1$ growing with distance r from the position of an observer at $r_0 = 0$. For weak fields,

$$\sqrt{A} \approx 1 + \frac{\Phi}{c^2}, \quad (20)$$

where Φ is the potential of the gravitational field [6].

Combing eq. (20) with eq. (8), the entropy, describing the content of transmitted information per time unit is now

$$\sigma_1 = \log\left(\left(1 + \frac{\Phi}{c^2}\right) \cdot \exp\left(-a \cdot \frac{r}{c(t-t_0)}\right)\right) \quad (21)$$

For weak fields, $\log\left(1 + \frac{\Phi}{c^2}\right) \approx \frac{\Phi}{c^2}$; due to eq. (19), we get two opposite accelerations

$$\frac{g_1}{c^2} = -\sigma_1' = -\frac{1}{c^2} \cdot \frac{d\Phi}{dr} + a \cdot \frac{1}{c(t-t_0)}. \quad (22)$$

They express the gravitational compression and the entropic expansion for $t > t_0$.

In a simple model, we consider the present universe as a spherical system with a constant number of identical point particles, the galaxies, with gravitating mass M , radius R and constant spatial density. The averaged energy u of one particle due to the gravitational interaction is $u = -\frac{3}{5} \frac{G \cdot M}{R}$. Since the averaged distance r of two particles in the universe is proportional to R , we have $u = -k \cdot \frac{1}{r}$ with an appropriate constant k . So, the gravitational acceleration in eq. (22),

$g_{grav} = -\frac{d\Phi}{dr}$, is proportional to $-\frac{1}{r^2}$. In the future, for large values of the coordinate time t , $\sqrt{B} \approx 1$; so, the proper time τ flows proportional to the coordinate time t and the averaged distance r of masses moving on geodesics is growing proportional to the proper time τ (see Fig. 2); so, due to the entropic acceleration, in the future, dissipation dominates gravitation in eq. (22).

Comparing our geometrical approach with thermodynamics, we require thermalization of the particles and infer a uniform temperature T . The one-particle entropy S is given by

$$S = k_B \cdot \sigma_1 = \frac{u}{T} - \frac{H}{T}. \quad (23)$$

Here, u is the inner energy of one particle, k_B is the Boltzmann constant and H is the free Helmholtz energy. In an ideal gas, $H = -k_B \cdot T \cdot \log Z_1$ describes the number of possible positions $Z_1 = V/V_0$ which can be randomly 'chosen' if V_0 is the minimal required volume per particle. As is well known, in an ideal gas, dissipation is driven by the growth of entropy without any change of energy. In a real gas, entropy is responsible, that the gas dissipates against the attracting molecular forces thereby cooling down. Thus, there are two forces $F = F_1 + F_2$:

$$F = -T \cdot \frac{\partial S}{\partial r} = -\frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial H}{\partial r} \quad (24)$$

a contracting potential force F_1 and a dissipating force F_2 , which is connected with the change of free Helmholtz energy. In our approach, we replace the 'free choice' of positions by the 'free choice' of the disponible time interval, so $\frac{V}{V_0}$ by \sqrt{B} . Then, using eq. (19)

$$\frac{\partial H}{\partial r} = k_B \cdot T \cdot \frac{g}{c^2}. \quad (25)$$

The energy afforded to the expansion against the contracting force F_1 leads to the cooling of the system. On the other hand, the growth of entropy in irreversible processes is not necessarily accompanied by a change of energy; nevertheless, it can be measured in terms of energy, if an alternative reversible process is considered with initial and final states equal to those in the irreversible process. In our context, the energetic relation eq. (13) gives the energy according to an imagined reversible expansion of the universe, which is driven by the entropic force F_2 . It is positive, expressing the energy available in such a reversible process due to the expansion.

10. Effects leading to redshift of radiation

We consider monochromatic light which is emitted by a source moving along a geodesic line. The frequency f of light emitted from distance r_1 at the moment τ_1 and detected at $r_0 = 0$ at the later time τ_0 is shifted due to

- The alteration of the time dilatation during the runtime $\tau_0 - \tau_1$ of the light from the source to the detector due to the time-dependence of the metric.
- The time dilation in the distance r_1 due to the location dependence of the metric, see Fig. 1.
- The Doppler shift caused by the escape velocity of the source, see Fig. 2.

The shift of the wavelength $\lambda = \frac{c}{f}$ of light emitted in the past from distance r_1 and detected at $r_0 = 0$ is

$$z(r) = \frac{\lambda(r_1) - \lambda(r_0)}{\lambda(r_0)}. \quad (26)$$

Underlying our metric eq. (8), the time development and the distance dependence of \sqrt{B} are balanced during the flying time $\tau_0 - \tau_1$ of light traveling back from the distance r_1 in the direction of an observer at $r_0 = 0$; so, we are intitled to neglect the effect a) and b). By using local coordinates $(c \cdot \tau, r)$, we are allowed to look at the propagation of light as in a Minkowski diagram (Fig. 3). Regarding c), the observer notices individual velocities v of the bodies rushing away; at his local time τ_0 , the observer receives monochromatic light which has been emitted at different times from the bodies. With growing flying time $\tau_0 - \tau_1$ of the light and thus growing distance $r_1 = c \cdot (\tau_0 - \tau_1)$, the escape velocities $\beta = \frac{v}{c}$ of the light emitting bodies increase and thus the Doppler shifts

$$z = \sqrt{\frac{1+\beta}{1-\beta}} - 1 \quad (27)$$

of the emitted radiation. A value $z = 1$ corresponds to $\beta = 0,6$; This escape velocity is much higher than the relative velocities of individual galaxies, inversely as in the diffusion of molecules in gases.

We assume that bodies can drift apart at different initial speeds $v_0 \geq 0$ after the big bang. Based on Fig. (2), neglecting the retarding effect of gravity and relative velocities, we assume that the motion of different bodies is uniform. In linear approximation, we take into account the influence of gravity by assuming that the escape velocities at time τ_1 are somewhat reduced compared to the uniform motion with v_0 . We express this effect by a correction factor $b \leq 1$. So, in Fig. 3, light is emitted from a body with velocity

$$\beta = \frac{b \cdot r_1}{c \cdot \tau_0 - r_1} \quad (28)$$

in distance r_1 at time τ_1 and registered at time τ_0 . Since the redshift data [9] cover distances with $r_1 \ll c \cdot \tau_0$, we have

$$z \approx \sqrt{1 + \frac{2b \cdot r_1}{c \cdot \tau_0}} - 1 = \sqrt{1 + \frac{2 \cdot H_0}{c} \cdot b \cdot r_1} - 1. \quad (29)$$

The Hubble constant is $H_0 = \frac{1}{\tau_0}$.

Fig. 4 shows the graph of eq. 29 with value $\frac{H_0}{c} = 0,16/\text{Gps}$. The graph is not fitted to experimental data, but shows the feature, that $z(r)$ deviates from the Hubble law of the cosmological redshift. Underlying the RW-metric, this feature is responsible for the assumption of dark energy to exist. Since the Hubble residual for $z \leq 1$ is small, b is only slightly less than one.

For small distances r , we may expand eq. (29) to get

$$z \approx \frac{H_0}{c} \cdot b \cdot r. \quad (30)$$

This Hubble approximation is marked in Fig. 4 as dashed line.

In our approach, the Doppler shift of the radiation corresponds to the emission time $\tau_1 < \tau_0$. So, we can detect bodies emitting radiation only at times $\tau_1 > \frac{1}{2} \tau_0$. Recently, new observations showed massive galaxies with $7,4 < z <$

9,1, only 500 – 700 Myr after the big bang, when interpreted in the framework of the standard model of cosmology [10]. In our approach, such high values of z need not correspond to times $\tau_1 \ll \tau_0$.

Fig. 3. Sketch of the expanding universe as seen by an observer based on its local coordinate system.

Fig. 4. Redshift z of the radiation which is emitted from bodies in the distance r . The straight line is drawn assuming the Hubble law.

References

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